

THE ACTIVITIES AND TASKS OF THE STYLIST IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Khasanova Shakhnoza

Khiva city, Khorezm region, Uzbekistan, methodist of state pre-school education organization number 7

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8267820>

Abstract: This article provides complete information about the activity and duties of a teacher in pre-school education organizations. Implementation of educational work at the level of demand in the preschool educational organization, formation of the skills of strict adherence to labor discipline in educators, critical attitude to each other's shortcomings, increase of work efficiency by increasing work and creative activity, decision-making process Ensuring timely and high-quality implementation requires the trainer to have high knowledge and skills, the ability to work with educators taking into account their mentality, great experience and many spiritual qualities.

Key words: leader, methodist, method, training, discipline, personality.

Implementation of educational work at the level of demand in the preschool educational organization, formation of the skills of strict adherence to labor discipline in educators, critical attitude to each other's shortcomings, increase of work efficiency by increasing work and creative activity, decision-making process Ensuring timely and high-quality implementation requires the trainer to have high knowledge and skills, the ability to work with educators taking into account their mentality, great experience and many spiritual qualities. Therefore, taking into account that every young professional who is just starting his work needs help and advice, it is appropriate to connect him to a coach with sufficient knowledge and experience. The stylist must be a personal example in managing the team, that is, he takes the lead in doing all the work.

In general, there are many cases of replacing the word "leader" with the term "leader" in many literatures. In our opinion, the term "leader" cannot fully express the psychological characteristics of a "leader". The word "leader" is used in relation to a group, a person who influences its members and leads to a goal. Leadership is a state of a person determined by analyzing the structure of the group and the system of relations in it. But there are a number of other aspects that represent the quality of a leader, which we cannot analyze only within the framework of the relationship system. In this interpretation, it is necessary to take into account one of the main aspects characteristic of a leader - the ability of a person to act in accordance with the situation. Initiative, ingenuity and skill in solving a problem in a problem situation are characteristic qualities of a leader. In a difficult situation related to solving a problem, a leader is distinguished by his progress and leadership compared to others.

In our opinion, in the Uzbek language, these two expressions - "peshkadam" and "yetakchi" - can fully express the essence of a leader. In our opinion, the word "Leader" comes from a person's desire to lead a group. The phrase "leader" means that a person with certain qualities follows the group, and that the group chooses the path of the person it trusts at its own discretion. The same situation should be used in relation to the expression "leader". This

characteristic of a leader is manifested in his emotional appeal, in the virtue of attracting others to himself. Thus, replacing the word "leader" only with the term "leader" narrows the psychological interpretation of the leadership situation. Based on this consideration, we believe that it is better to use the word "leader". In addition, understanding the explanatory meaning of the word "leader" is familiar to the Uzbek reader.

Leadership and strategy. Each employee in the work team has his own position in the group. This position may be acquired formally or informally. The official position is represented by the position of the employee in the career ladder and the powers arising from his position. As any employee interacts with his colleagues, under the influence of various factors, these relationships begin to acquire an emotional color.

Relationships based on feelings are formed in two forms - liking (sympathy) and dislike (antipathy). There are employees who, with their certain qualities, can arouse the sympathy of most members of the team, and they occupy a high position in the informal system of the group. According to the psychological interpretation, an employee who occupies a high position in the official system of the team is considered a strategist, and a person who occupies a high position in the informal system is a leader.

A leadership position usually takes place within the group's informal relationship system. Recognition of a person at the level of a leader means emotional closeness to him, high evaluation of a number of his work-related qualities, and attention to the interests of the group. A leader is a person recognized by all members of the group. The main aspect of the leader's value system is to put the interests of the group above all else, to always seriously engage in solving the task set before the group, and to be able to mobilize the team in this process. The leader in the work team is distinguished primarily by his work characteristics, because he begins to stand out from others precisely because of his work. In addition, the leader, while protecting the interests of the group, can sometimes go against the system of official relations and the interests of official circles. As a result, a conflict may arise between the formal and informal leader in the team. Based on the interests of the enterprise, it is the most optimal case that the leader formed in the formal and informal system of the team is represented by one person. Modern psychology, through its achievements, can provide sufficient information about the nature of qualities characteristic of a leader and the ways to achieve them. In this regard, we can include the characteristics of a leader into three categories:

- 1) focus on the interests of the community;
- 2) professional skill, taking the initiative in solving the problem in any problem situation and taking the initiative;
- 3) emotional, emotional attractiveness characteristics; The sequence of the set of features listed above also has its own logic.

Research has shown that emotional appeal does not necessarily have to be very prominent in a leader. The average presence of this indicator in a person is enough for him to be recognized at the leadership level. But the low level of emotional attractiveness characteristic of a person can have a negative effect on business communication and negotiations. A stylist's ability to create a positive impression on others by knowing the secrets of communication is the main tool for increasing this indicator. Stewardship is an appointed position, and leadership is a position promoted by like-minded people. If we pay attention to the difference between a methodical leader, we can list many aspects. For example, if the facilitator has employees, the

leader has like-minded supporters, if the facilitator is appointed, the leader is isolated from the team members, if the facilitator is based on his authority, and the leader relies on his reputation. The stylist puts the interest of the organization in the first place according to his commitment, and this characteristic gives him an official tone and puts him in a somewhat "weak" position in front of the team in relation to the leader. In life, there are many teams in which the official methodical leader consists of individuals. In many situations in the life of such a team, it is likely that the group members will be on the side of the informal leader rather than the mastermind. The relationship between a formal and an informal leader in a team is always a difficult issue. In such a situation, it is usually observed that most strategists try to squeeze the leader and get rid of him, while another strategist can use this leader and mobilize him to achieve the group's goal faster. The stylist's ability to get along with the leader and agree is a guarantee of future success. For this, resourcefulness, patience and the ability to rise above one's own interests are raised from the designer. When a formal group leader is made up of diverse individuals, disagreements between them are perceived by many employees as a violation of social justice.

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